

POSTMODERNIST INTERPRETATION OF THE ORPHANS MOTIF

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Abstract: This essay discusses artistic writing connected to the theme of orphanhood. Artistic analysis is conducted on modern literary instances of the orphanhood motif, as well as the modernist image of orphans.

Key words: social problem, poetry, modernist, postmodernist interpretation.

"The earliest concepts regarding the picture can be found in Aristotle's book "Poetics". It uses the term mimesis rather than image. The term mimesis refers to the imitation of nature. In ancient global literature, it is clear that a conscious understanding of certain persons' commonalities emerged. The Greek philosopher Aristotle, who theoretically supported this view, noted in his aforementioned book that poetry, as opposed to history, is based on more broad features; poetry talks about more general happenings, whilst history informs about specific events (Aristotle, 1980).

The narrative of the "Orphan House" by acclaimed writer Zulfia Kuroloy depicts the societal challenges created by orphan hood. In the novel, Rano, who became an orphan after his mother died at an early age, fled from home to the city when his stepmother planned to marry her nephew at the age of sixteen, demonstrating that the human mind is a problem with no cure.

The names of A. Yoldosh's "Orphan Word" (Yuldosh A., 2017) and Z. Kuroloy's "Orphan House" tales are similarly reminiscent of the current trend. The theme of orphanhood in the stories is completely separate from other works written in prose; the characters are in a different world, and their thinking is incompatible with the individuals of the outside world; these characters have worlds that only they understand and strive for, which is not possible for ordinary people in society.

The orphan hood concept may also be seen in Nazar Eshankul's novella "A premature bong" (Eshanql N., 2018). In it, the modern interpretation of the hero's character manifests itself in the shape of an inner spiritual revolt of a heavy, sad individual.

When he was a youngster, his mother went to the harvest to ask for bread, and he witnessed her being raped in front of him. Although the picture of the guard who murdered and killed the secretary who insulted his mother is a little one, the insults directed at his mother jolted his sleeping honor and desire.

This artwork is not intended to grieve or inform others about the shame of being an orphan.

An unforgettable, one-of-a-kind individual who grows accustomed to his difficulties and softly absorbs them. A person who has been unable to overcome his childhood humiliation and continues to live with the sorrow of those memories. In the psychologism of the ambiguous hero, who silently took orphan hood, humiliation, and humiliation, did not expect too much from fate, and continued to live as he was, there is a short spiritual outburst, a burst of yearning to get rid of everything, to free himself of the heavy weight. The beat is evocative of the current approach of the hero becoming anti-refusal. N. Eshonkul describes this orphan hero as someone who has not fully discovered and comprehended himself. S. Vafo's work "Ovora's Seen and Forgiveness" has an episodic picture of an orphan. In the novel "Ovora's Seen and Suffered," there are instances in which Madina's episodic picture appears in the mind of the main character Saltanat Mahmud; he is unable to fully evaluate it, explain this scenario, and exhibits a chaotic expression of psychology.

In 2020, Javlon Jovliyev's novel "Don't Be Afraid," which sparked debate among many literary critics, the peculiar poetic expressions of the ideas of a six-month-old orphan who knows everything, may be viewed with a postmodernist perspective. Based on the aforementioned factors, the following conclusions may be drawn:

1. In Uzbek prose from the independence period, the issue of orphanhood and the image of an orphan are dominated by creative interpretation in the framework of historical memory and diaries' epic thinking traditions.

2. Lyric observation and creative analysis of the origins and repercussions of orphan hood are recurring themes in this period's literature.

3. In conclusion, our findings revealed that the orphan theme is not discussed in the interpretation of the image of an orphan in modernist and postmodernist works, orphan hood is not highlighted, there is an orphan plot, but the word orphan is not defined. The idea of inner psychologism is central to the poetics of the orphanage motif.

Orphan hood serves as a motif and topic for illuminating the human inner self and artistically interpreting his emotional pain.

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